

Student Attitude Towards Yoga and Their Peace of Mind at Secondary School of West Bengal

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Abstract

Today Frustration, Anxiety, Mental Stress, Mental related diseases etc. Are increasing in our society. Due to these diseases many persons including the students feels Isolation, Anger, Confusion, Depression, Mood disorders, Attention deficit-hyperactive disorder, Obsessive disorder, Adjustment disorder etc. Under the effect of on top of Mental related disorders the level of students' Exam's Achievements are much low. The training of 'Yoga' would give the proper direction for the betterment in Exam's achievements & much give positive peace of mind. The present study try to provide a clearcut concept of the students' attitude towards yoga and their present status of peace of mind. A quantitative descriptive survey done on 200 randomised sample which analyzed through MS Excel.

Key words: Yoga, Attitude towards Yoga, Peace of Mind

Introduction

Yoga is a spiritual science of self-realization. It comes from India and goes back over 5000 of years. The Indian sage Patanjali, in his yoga sutras defines yoga as the control of the activities of the mind. Yoga methods encompass the entire field of our existence, from the physical emotional and mental to the spiritual. Its methods includes ethical declines , physical postures, breath control as well as meditation.

Classical yoga as defined by Patanjali is an eight stages process of spiritual development (the eight limbs of yoga). The first two stages are ethical disciplines (Yamas and Nyamas). Then come postures (Asanas in Sanskrit) and breathing exercises (Pranayama). The last four limbs are meditative stages: control of the sense (Prathyara), concentration (Dharana), meditation (Dhyana) and enlightenment (Samadhi). Yoga is a spiritual science of self-realization. It comes from india and goes back over 5000 of years. The indian sage Patanjali, in his yoga sutras defines yoga as the controll of the activities of the mind. Yoga methods encompass the entire field of our existence, from the physical emotional and mental to the spiritual. Its methods includes ethical declines , physical postures, breath controll as well as meditation.

Yoga has become a very common term in the Western world today, and yoga classes can be found in virtually every town. Most Westerners identify yoga with hatha yoga. Hatha yoga seeks to promote health and well-being through physical exercise. The regular practice of asanas, and breathing exercises (pranayama), makes the body strong, supple and healthy. It has a profound effect on the circulation and on the functioning of the inner organs, glands and nerves, keeping all systems in radiant health and leading to greater energy, better concentration, and a happier, more fulfilling life. Many common physical ailments can also be improved through the regular practice of yoga, and it is never too late or too early in life to take it up. Anyone can practice yoga. Nowadays, one can learn yoga in lesser spiritual set-ups due to the availability of video instructionals and internet tutorials. It is s Anxiety, Mental Stress eTodaytc. Mental related diseases are increasing in our society.

Due somewhat a debate whether yoga's essence has faded because of videos and such. Although there are still real yoga practitioners in real meditative set-ups and hopefully the tradition stays. There has been film production and documentaries in the past about yoga. Some of which were experimental, vivid and filmed in a cinematic way like nico beyer visual sequences.

Background of the study

In pursuance of the decision of Cabinet Committee on Economic Affairs (CCEA), Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has transferred four components of the "Scheme on Quality Improvement in Schools" to National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT). "Introduction of Yoga in Schools" is one of the components to be implemented by NCERT. This component has been transferred to PSSCIVE (a constituent of NCERT), Bhopal in 2012. Yoga has been an integral part of the subject "Health and Physical Education", which is a compulsory subject up to the secondary school stage. The NCF-2005 adopted a holistic definition of health, in which yoga is an integral part. Both yoga and physical education contribute both to the physical development of the child and also to the psychosocial and mental development. Thus, if Yoga practice contributes to the overall development of the child. Studies have shown that yoga contributes to flexibility and muscular fitness. Also it can help correct the postural defects among school children. Also yoga helps in coping up with the concerns related to the process of growing up. It counters stresses and strains. Also it helps in reducing the stress. Both yoga and physical education are seen as routes for achieving overall development of children. Due to the reasons mentioned above, both yoga and physical education have to be given the due importance in the school education. They can contribute to the quality of school education in general and to health and physical development in particular. This Yoga scheme, therefore, focuses on preparing trained teachers for yoga education and training in Indian schools. The teachers training programme on Yoga conducted under this scheme need to be based on the stipulations made in the National Curriculum Framework (NCF) -2005 and the syllabi of Health and Physical Education prepared by NCERT for various classes of school education.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are as under.

O1: To study the Student attitude towards Yoga in secondary school of west Bengal.

O2: To study the Peace of mind of secondary school of west Bengal.

O3: To study the relationship between the attitude towards Yoga and the Peace of mind of secondary school students of west Bengal.

Objective wise Hypotheses

The following Major hypotheses were formulated for the present study.

For Objective 1-

H₀1 : There would be no significant difference in boys and girls student attitude towards Yoga.

H₀2 : There would be no significant difference in urban and rural student attitude towards Yoga.

For Objective 2-

H₀3: There would be no significant difference in boys and girls student in their peace of mind.

H₀4 : There would be no significant difference in urban and rural student in their peace of mind.

For Objective 3-

H₀5: There would be no significant correlation between student attitude towards Yoga and their peace of mind.

Delimitation

(1) The study was delimited to Bengali medium School students of west Bengal only.

(2) The study was delimited to 4 District only.

(3) The study was delimited to 8 schools only.

Operational definition of the terms used

Attitude of Yoga

Yoga means 'union' or 'connection'. Conscious connection to something allows us to feel and experience that thing, person, or experience. The experience of connection is a state of yoga, a joyful and blissful, fulfilling experience. Awareness is the secret of yoga. It claims to improve health and happiness. Attitude is defined as "a complex mental state involving beliefs and feeling"(Latchanna & Dagnev, 2009). Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing, or event. What about the feeling, beliefs, views of students towards yoga may identify through the study.

Peace of mind

Peace of mind is a state of mental and emotional calmness, with no worries, fears or stress. In this state, the mind is quiet, and you experience a sense of happiness and freedom.

Design of the study

In order to get proper reflection as per objectives, the descriptive survey research method would be used. Descriptive and inferential statistics would be employed to analyze data for reaching a valid and generalized conclusion.

Sample

The sample selected randomly from the students from different west Bengal secondary schools. The students from co-ed schools under west Bengal. 200 students taken as sample by randomised way for this study.

Sample structure			
AREA	BOYS	GIRLS	TOTAL
URBAN	50	50	100
RURAL	50	50	100
TOTAL	100	100	200

Variables

Major variables:

- i. Attitude towards Yoga
- ii. Peace of mind

Categorical variables:

- i. Sex (boys & girls)
- ii. Locality (rural & urban)

Tools

Two self made questionnaire (Viz. SATY- Student Attitude Towards Yoga & PMS- Peace of mind scale) will be used for this present study with an interview with secondary school teacher.

Procedure of Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher visited to the school personally and to the school students given short instruction regarding the filling in of their response. After that, the tool proceed to them and the required approximately 30 to 40 minutes for completing. Collected data is tabulated and organized for presentation, analysis and interpretation. Descriptive statistical analyses, inferential statistical analyses and correlation statistical analyses used for data analysis. Descriptive statistic like mean, standard deviation are calculate for the all groups and all scores. After that inferential statistic like ‘t’-test and correlation statistic like ‘Pearson Correlation’ is applied. The significance of ‘t’ values tested at 0.05 level of significance. Whole data analyzed through MS Excel.

Hypotheses testing

Testing of H₀₁:

H₀₁- There would be no significant difference in boys and girls student attitude towards Yoga.

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
MALE	100	109.45	2.544	0.254
FEMALE	100	108.62	2.513	0.251

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	-2.320*	198	0.021

(* Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation:

Table 4.2 shows that in case of Attitude towards yoga between boy and girl students, the calculate $t_{(198)}$ value is 2.320 and ‘p’ value is 0.021 ($p > .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is not significant at 0.05 levels. So, H₀₁ is not rejected and it can be safely said that boy students are not significantly different from girl students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga .

Testing of H₀₂:

H₀₂ : There would be no significant difference in urban and rural student attitude towards Yoga.

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
RURAL	100	108.56	2.555	0.255
URBAN	100	109.51	2.480	0.248

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	-2.667*	198	0.008

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation:

Table 4.4 shows that in case of Attitude towards yoga between urban and rural students, the calculate $t_{(198)}$ value is 2.667 and ‘p’ value is 0.008 ($p < .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is significant at 0.05 levels. So, H₀₂ is rejected and it

can be safely said that urban students are significantly different from rural students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga .

Testing of H₀₃:

H₀₃: There would be no significant difference in boys and girls student in their peace of mind.

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
FEMALE	100	148.65	10.799	1.079
MALE	100	142.48	11.813	1.181

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	3.854*	198	0.000

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation:

Table 4.6 shows that in case of Peace of mind between male and female students, the calculate $t_{(198)}$ value is 3.854 and ‘p’ value is 0.000 ($p < .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is significant at 0.05 levels. So, H₀₃ is rejected and it can be safely said that male students are significantly different from female students in respect to their Peace of mind.

Testing of H₀₄:

H₀₄ : There would be no significant difference in Rural and Urban student in their peace of mind.

GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Rural	100	144.36	11.426	1.142
Urban	100	146.77	11.913	1.191

Equal variances assumed	t-test for Equality of Means		
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	-1.459*	198	0.145

(* Not Significant at 0.05 level of significance)

Interpretation:

Table 4.8 shows that in case of Peace of mind between rural and urban students, the calculate $t_{(198)}$ value is 1.459 and ‘p’ value is 0.145 ($p > .05$). Hence, ‘t’ is not significant at 0.05 levels. So, H₀₄ is not rejected and it can be safely said that rural students are not significantly different from urban students in respect to their Peace of mind.

Testing of H₀₅:

H₀₅: There would be no significant correlation between student attitude towards Yoga and their peace of mind.

Groups: Boys student and Girls student

	attitude towards yoga	peace of mind
attitude towards yoga	1	
peace of mind	0.512	1

Interpretation:

From the analysis in Table No 4.9 it is seen that in the Pearson Correlation the 'r' value is .512 between scores of attitude towards yoga and peace of mind. Hence, H_0 is significant. So, it can be safely said that attitude towards yoga and peace of mind is correlated.

The major findings:

- ❖ Boy students are not significantly different from girl students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga .
- ❖ Urban students are significantly different from rural students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga .
- ❖ Male students are significantly different from female students in respect to their Peace of mind.
- ❖ Rural students are not significantly different from urban students in respect to their Peace of mind.
- ❖ The attitude towards yoga and peace of mind in secondary level student is correlated.

Discussion

- i. Boy students are not significantly different from girl students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga. The mean score of Boys student (109.45) of attitude towards yoga was higher than the Girls student (108.62). It means that boy student possesses more positive attitude than the girl student.
- ii. Urban students are significantly different from rural students in respect to their Attitude towards yoga. The mean score of urban student (109.51) of attitude towards yoga was higher than the Rural student (108.56). It means that urban student possesses more positive attitude than the rural students.
- iii. Male students are significantly different from female students in respect to their Peace of mind. The mean score of female student (148.65) of Peace of mind was higher than the male student (142.48). It means that female student possesses more positive Peace of mind than the male student.
- iv. Rural students are not significantly different from urban students in respect to their Peace of mind. The mean score of urban student (146.77) of Peace of mind was higher than the rural student (144.36). It means that urban student possesses more positive Peace of mind than the rural student.
- v. The attitude towards yoga and peace of mind in secondary level student is positively correlated.

Educational implication

- ❖ The present study helps to understand students' attitude in yoga in west bengal.
- ❖ The present study helps to understand students' peace situation in west bengal.
- ❖ The present study helps to understand the interrelationship between students' attitude and students' peace situation in yoga in west bengal.
- ❖ The present study may help to educational policy making as well as planing.

Conclusion

The whole study laid its focus on attitude towards yoga and peace of mind of secondary level students of west Bengal. Researcher got a result after completion his research work that the students of west bengal have positive attitude towards yoga as well as they have positive peace of mind. Here, researcher also found that there lays a moderate positive correlation between attitude towards yoga and peace of mind of students. Hence, researcher can say that if the family, school authority or government take some active initiatives to promote any one that will influence another to grow up.

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